

Abundance of heterotrophic marine bacteria, *Vibrio*, and marine fungi in green seaweed *Caulerpa racemosa* in Sibutu, Tawi-Tawi, Philippines

Albaris B. Tahiluddin^{1*}

^{1*}College of Fisheries, Mindanao State University-Tawi-Tawi College of Technology and Oceanography, Bongao, Tawi-Tawi, 7500, Philippines.

Citation

Tahiluddin, A.B, Daganio, J.M., Lodovice, R.S., & Umpay, M.J.G. (2022). Abundance of Heterotrophic Marine Bacteria, *Vibrio*, and Marine Fungi in Green Seaweed *Caulerpa racemosa* in Sibutu, Tawi-Tawi, Philippines. *Sustainable Aquatic Research*, 1(2), 56-62.

Artical History

Received: 19 June 2022

Received in revised form: 4 August 2022

Accepted: 4 August 2022

Available online: 30 August 2022

Corresponding Author

Albaris Tahiluddin

E-mail: albarist20@gmail.com

Tel: +639094260941

Keywords

Caulerpa racemosa var. *occidentalis*

Heterotrophic marine bacteria

Marine fungi

Vibrio

Abstract

Seaweeds have been used in the human diet for centuries, particularly in Asia. Green seaweed from the genus of *Caulerpa* is consumed throughout the Pacific and Southeast Asia, with high economic value. In the Philippines, *Caulerpa* spp. are one of the seaweed delicacies among locals eaten as salads. In Tawi-Tawi, southern Philippines, *Caulerpa racemosa* var. *occidentalis* is one of the edible seaweeds which is sold in the market center in Bongao, Tawi-Tawi and Tongehat, Sibutu, Tawi-Tawi is one of the sources of this seaweed. However, the microbial load of this green seaweed has not yet been explored and has remained unstudied. Hence, in this study, we determined the microbial load (colony-forming unit, CFU) of heterotrophic marine bacteria, *Vibrio*, and marine fungi from *C. racemosa* var. *occidentalis* in coastal waters of Tongehat, Sibutu, Tawi-Tawi, Philippines, following the serial dilution procedure. Results revealed that the heterotrophic marine bacteria recorded the highest abundance of 5.9×10^{10} CFU g⁻¹. *Vibrio* abundance was 1.2×10^2 CFU g⁻¹, and marine fungi load was 4.1×10^3 CFU g⁻¹. The low presence of *Vibrio* in this study indicates that the *C. racemosa* var. *occidentalis* contains low potential pathogens and may be safe for human consumption.

spreading rapidly in western countries (Løvdaal et al., 2021). *Caulerpa* genus is a

Introduction

Seaweeds are important coastal products that are commonly used as a food source (Delan et al., 2015), and they have been utilized in human diet for decades in Asia, and now also

green seaweed, commonly called as “seagrapes,” popularly consumed in the

Pacific and Southeast Asian countries (Paul et al., 2014). *Caulerpa racemosa*, one of the species of seagrapes with high economic value, contains many nutritional components and can be used as a functional food item for humans (Magdugo et al., 2020). Compared to other seaweeds, it contains a greater amount of protein, crude lipids, and fiber (Bhuiyan et al., 2016). Hence, some local people of the Northern Philippines utilize *C. racemosa* as a traditional medicine to relieve cough or asthma (Dumilag and Javier, 2022).

Seaweed diversity in the Philippines is high, with a total of 1291 seaweed species (Ang et al., 2013). Among these, the most important genera are *Kappaphycus*, *Eucheuma*, *Gracilaria*, *Caulerpa* (Trono and Largo, 2019), and *Sargassum* (Yangson et al., 2022); all these seaweeds are commercially cultivated throughout the country (Trono and Largo, 2019; Tahiluddin et al., 2021a; Tahiluddin et al., 2021b; Tahiluddin et al., 2021c; Estrada et al., 2021; Sarri et al., 2022; Dumilag et al., 2022; Tahiluddin et al., 2022a; Tahiluddin et al., 2022b), except for *Sargassum*, which is still in its infancy (Yangson et al., 2022). In Tawi-Tawi, Philippines, *C. racemosa* is one of the edible seaweeds that is abundant in the local market, normally prepared by the consumers as a salad mixed with vinegar, tomatoes, and onions, and is considered as one of the essential traditional diets of the local people (Dumilag, 2019). This green seaweed is usually collected from its natural habitat. One of the important sources of *Caulerpa* species in the local market of Tawi-Tawi, is the Sibutu Island, particularly in the coastal water of Tongehat village.

Microbial communities thriving on the surface of the seaweeds are very complex, dynamic, and composed of a consortium of microorganisms, including fungi, bacteria, diatoms, spores, protozoa, and marine invertebrate larvae (Singh and Reddy, 2014). The abundance of microorganisms can be used as an indicator of the food quality and safety of edible seaweeds. For instance, the seaweed's high bacterial load may indicate

the health and age of the plant and may negatively affect the sensory quality and shelf-life of the product, but it does not imply that it is unsafe to eat. On the other hand, low bacterial counts do not necessarily imply that it is safe since some pathogens, such as *Vibrio*, even a small numbers, are sufficient to cause serious human health problems (Løvdal et al., 2021). Moreover, *Vibrio* and marine fungi are normally associated with seaweeds in the natural marine environment (Tahiluddin and Terzi, 2021a; Tahiluddin and Terzi, 2021b; Tahiluddin et al., 2021c; Bermil et al., 2022). The presence of opportunistic *Vibrio* and marine fungi can cause ice-ice disease in red seaweeds (Zainuddin et al., 2019; Bermil et al., 2022). In green seaweeds, like *Caulerpa* species, *Vibrio* and marine fungi are naturally occurring microorganisms (Rizzo et al., 2013; Rizzo et al., 2016; Kataržytė et al., 2017). In this study, we investigated the abundance of microorganisms, such as heterotrophic marine bacteria, *Vibrio*, and marine fungi in green seaweed *C. racemosa* var. *occidentalis* in Sibutu, Tawi-Tawi, southern Philippines. This would serve as part of a baseline information when it comes to microbial loads of *C. racemosa* var. *occidentalis* since this green seaweed is consumed by the local people in the area and nearby places.

Materials and Methods

Study Site

Seagrape *C. racemosa* var. *occidentalis* samples were collected from coastal waters of Tongehat, Sibutu, Tawi-Tawi, Philippines (Figure 1) and analyzed at Microbiology Laboratory, College of Fisheries (COF), Mindanao State University Tawi-Tawi College of Technology and Oceanography (MSU-TCTO), Sanga-Sanga, Bongao, Tawi-Tawi from March 31 to April 23, 2019.

Figure 1. Map of the sampling site

Collection of Samples

About 10 grams of a whole part of healthy *C. racemosa* var. *occidentalis* were collected and placed in a sealed sterile glass jar containing 200 ml of sterile seawater. These samples were placed in disinfected styrofoam with sterile seawater ice in order to chill the samples and were immediately transferred to a freezer in Tongehat, Sibutu.

Transporting of Samples

The frozen samples in a sealed sterile glass jar were placed in clean and disinfected styrofoam together with seawater ice. These were transported from the sampling site to Microbiology Laboratory, COF, MSU-TCTO, Sanga-Sanga, Bongao, Tawi-Tawi for 3.5 hours. The samples were immediately frozen again for 24 hours before analysis.

Microbial Analysis

The microbial analysis of the seagrapes samples was carried out under sterile conditions following the method of Tahiluddin et al. (2021c). One (1) gram of sample was chopped using a sterile razor blade and forceps and placed in a test tube with 9 ml diluent (0.1% peptone with 0.85% NaCl). This was mixed for 2-3 minutes using a vortex mixer. One (1) ml was diluted to the next test tube with 9 ml diluent and serially diluted up to 10¹¹ dilutions for the heterotrophic marine bacteria, 10³ dilutions for the *Vibrio*, and 10⁴ dilutions for the marine fungi. An aliquot of 0.1 ml of each dilution was spread-plated into marine agar (Scharlau), thiosulfate-citrate-bile salts-sucrose agar (TCBS; TM MEDIA), and malt extract agar (TM MEDIA) and incubated at room temperature for 2 days (heterotrophic marine bacteria and *Vibrio*)

and 14 days (marine fungi). Grown colonies were counted manually. The colony-forming units (CFU g⁻¹) were calculated using the formula (Maturin and Peeler, 2001).

$$N = \frac{\Sigma C}{[(1 \times n_1) + (1 \times n_2) + (1 \times n_3) \times (d)]}$$

Where:

N= Number of colonies per g of sample

ΣC= Sum of all colonies on all plates counted

n₁= Number of plates in first dilution counted

n₂= Number of plates in second dilution counted

d= Dilution from which the first counts were obtained.

Results and Discussion

The abundance of marine microorganisms from *C. racemosa* var. *occidentalis* is shown in Table 1. The heterotrophic marine bacterial load was found to be higher, reported at 5.9 x 10¹⁰ CFU g⁻¹. *Vibrio* count was low at 1.2 x 10² CFU g⁻¹, while the number of marine fungi was 4.1 x 10³ CFU g⁻¹.

Table 1. Abundance of marine microorganisms (CFU g⁻¹) from *Caulerpa racemosa* var. *occidentalis*

Microorganism	Microorganism count (CFU g ⁻¹)
Heterotrophic marine Bacteria	5.9 x 10 ¹⁰
<i>Vibrio</i>	1.2 x 10 ²
Marine Fungi	4.1 x 10 ³

The total heterotrophic marine bacterial count (5.9 x 10¹⁰ CFU g⁻¹) in *C. racemosa* var. *occidentalis* determined in this study was relatively greater than reported in *C. lentillifera* with an abundance of 10⁶ CFU g⁻¹ sampled from the water of Bohol, central Philippines (Delan et al., 2015) and 10⁷ CFU g⁻¹ obtained from the tank culture in Japan (Kudaka et al., 2008). In the Mediterranean Sea, the bacterial load of *C. cylindracea* was found to be 10⁷ CFU ml⁻¹. When compared with other green seaweed, our result was parallel to *Ulva lactuca* (10¹⁰ to 10¹² CFU g⁻¹) collected from the adjacent coastal water of our sampling site (Tahiluddin et al., 2021a).

Vibrio abundance in *C. racemosa* var. *occidentalis* in this study was relatively low at 1.2 x 10² CFU g⁻¹, 10 fold lower than reported by Rizzo et al. (2013) sampled from Brindisi, Italy. In the Mediterranean Sea, the abundance of *Vibrio* from *C. cylindracea* was found to be 10³ to 10⁴ CFU ml⁻¹ (Rizzo et al., 2016). In red seaweed

Kappaphycus striatus, the number of *Vibrio* was 10⁴ CFU g⁻¹ sampled in a similar site in this study (Tahiluddin et al., 2021c).

The marine fungal load in chlorophytes (green seaweed) ranged from 0.02 x 10⁴ to 1.2 x 10⁴ CFU g⁻¹ (Katarzytè et al., 2017). In this study, marine fungi associated with *C. racemosa* var. *occidentalis* had an count of 4.1 x 10³ CFU g⁻¹. In red seaweeds *K. alvarezii* and *K. striatus*, the load of marine fungi was 10² to 10³ and 10³ to 10⁴, respectively, investigated in the same sampling site of this study (Bermil et al., 2022). In mangrove-associated sponges, different marine fungi had a count of 10² CFU g⁻¹ (Calabon et al., 2019).

Microorganisms are naturally associated with seaweeds, which play a huge role in both the growth and morphogenesis of macroalgae in direct and/or indirect ways (Singh and Reddy, 2014). Hence, their abundance in *C. racemosa* determined in this study may reflect its natural microbiome and help in these roles.

However, the final microbial load may be higher than in the natural habitat since edible seaweeds may also get contaminated or re-contaminated while handling and processing until reaching the consumers' tables (Løvndal et al., 2021).

Conclusion

The collected *C. racemosa* var. *occidentalis* had a high load of heterotrophic marine bacteria, although it was in a good state. A low count of marine fungi was recorded, and the total of potentially pathogenic microorganisms such as *Vibrio* was also low. This study suggests that *C. racemosa* var. *occidentalis* harbors naturally occurring microorganisms, which may play important roles in the green seaweed. However, seagrapes that are marketed and displayed for sale, such as in the local public markets, need to be investigated as the final microbial load may be associated with poor handling and may lead to contamination of edible seagrapes.

Acknowledgment

The authors are grateful to Rosita T. Jumdain, Concepcion C. Toring, and Maria Liza B. Toring-Farquerabao.

Ethical approval

The author declares that this study complies with research and publication ethics.

Data availability statement

The authors declare that data are available from authors upon reasonable request.

Funding organizations

No funding available.

References

Ang Jr, P. O., Leung, S. M., & Choi, M. M. (2013). A verification of reports of marine algal species from the Philippines. *Philippine Journal of Science*, 142(3), 5-49.

Bermil, A. B., Hamisain, J.B.D., Tahiluddin, A. B., Jumdain, **R. J.** and Toring-

Farquerabao, M. L. B. (2022). Abundance of marine-derived fungi in nutrient-enriched *Kappaphycus* species. *Journal of Biometry Studies*, 2(1): 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.29329/JofBS.2022.444.01>

Bhuiyan, K. A., Qureshi, S., Mustafa Kamal, A. H., AftabUddin, S., & Siddique, A. (2016). Proximate chemical composition of sea grapes *Caulerpa racemosa* (J. Agardh, 1873) collected from a sub-tropical coast. *Virology & Mycology*, 5(158), 2161-0517.

Calabon, M. S., Sadaba, R. B., & Campos, W. L. (2019). Fungal diversity of mangrove-associated sponges from New Washington, Aklan, Philippines. *Mycology*, 10(1), 6-21.

Delan, G. G., Legados, J. A., Pepito, A. R., Cunado, V. D., Rica, R. L., Abdon, H. C., & Ilano, A. S. (2015). The Influence of habitat on the quality characteristics of the green macro alga *Caulerpa lentillifera* Agardh (Caulerpaceae, Chlorophyta). *Tropical Technology Journal*, 19(1), 1-7.

Dumilag, R. V. (2019). Edible seaweeds sold in the local public markets in Tawi-Tawi, Philippines. *Philippine Journal of Science*, 148, 803-811.

Dumilag, R. V., & Javier, R. F. (2022). Ethnobotany of medicinal seaweeds of Ilocos Norte, Philippines. *Philippine Journal of Science*, 151(3), 1135-1156.

Dumilag, R. V., Crisostomo, B. A., Aguinaldo, Z. Z. A., Hinaloc, L. A. R., Liao, L. M., Roa-Quiaoit, H. A., ... & Roleda, M. Y. (2022). The Diversity of eucheumatoid seaweed cultivars in the Philippines. *Reviews in Fisheries Science & Aquaculture*, 1-19.

Estrada, J. L., Arboleda, M. D. M., & Dionisio-Sese, M. L. (2021). Current status of sea grapes (*Caulerpa* spp.) farming and wild harvesting in the Philippines. *Journal of Applied Phycology*, 33(5), 3215-3223.

- FDA. (2001). *Bacteriological analytical manual chapter 3: Aerobic plate count*. Retrieved March 20, 2019, from <https://www.fda.gov/Food/FoodScienceResearch/LaboratoryMethods/ucm063346.htm>
- Kataržytė, M., Vaičiūtė, D., Bučas, M., Gyraitė, G., & Petkuvienė, J. (2017). Microorganisms associated with charophytes under different salinity conditions. *Oceanologia*, 59(2), 177-186.
- Kudaka, J., Itokazu, K., Taira, K., Nidaira, M., Okano, S., Nakamura, M., & Ohno, A. (2008). Investigation and culture of microbial contaminants of *Caulerpa lentillifera* (sea grape). *Shokuhin Eiseigaku zasshi. Journal of the Food Hygienic Society of Japan*, 49(1), 11-15.
- Løvdal, T., Lunestad, B. T., Myrmed, M., Rosnes, J. T., & Skipnes, D. (2021). Microbiological food safety of seaweeds. *Foods*, 10(11), 2719.
- Magdugo, R. P., Terme, N., Lang, M., Pliego-Cortés, H., Marty, C., Hurtado, A. Q., & Bourgougnon, N. (2020). An analysis of the nutritional and health values of *Caulerpa racemosa* (Forsskål) and *Ulva fasciata* (Delile)—Two chlorophyta collected from the Philippines. *Molecules*, 25(12), 2901.
- Maturin, L. J., & Peeler, J. T. (2001). Aerobic plate count. In *Bacteriological Analytical Manual*. FDA. <https://www.fda.gov/Food/FoodScienceResearch/LaboratoryMethods/ucm063346.htm>
- Paul, N. A., Neveux, N., Magnusson, M., & De Nys, R. (2014). Comparative production and nutritional value of “sea grapes”—the tropical green seaweeds *Caulerpa lentillifera* and *C. racemosa*. *Journal of applied phycology*, 26(4), 1833-1844.
- Rizzo, L., Frascchetti, S., Alifano, P., Tredici, M. S., & Stabili, L. (2016). Association of *Vibrio* community with the Atlantic Mediterranean invasive alga *Caulerpa cylindracea*. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 475, 129-136.
- Rizzo, L., Tredici, S., Pizzolante, G., Alifano, P., Stabili, L., & Frascchetti, S. (2013). *Vibrio* diversity associated with the invasive seaweed *Caulerpa racemosa* (Chlorophyta, Caulerpaceae). *Rapp. Comm. int. Mer Médit.*, 40.
- Sarri, J., Abdulmutalib, Y., Tilka, M. M., Terzi, E., & Tahiluddin, A. (2022). Effects of inorganic nutrient enrichment on the carrageenan yield, growth, and ice-ice disease occurrence of red alga *Kappaphycus striatus*. *Aquatic Research*, 5(2), 99-109.
- Singh, R. P., & Reddy, C. R. K. (2014). Seaweed–microbial interactions: key functions of seaweed-associated bacteria. *FEMS microbiology ecology*, 88(2), 213-230.
- Tahiluddin, A. B., Terzi, E. (2021a). Ice-ice disease in commercially cultivated seaweeds *Kappaphycus* spp. and *Eucheuma* spp.: A review on the causes, occurrence, and control measures. *Marine Science and Technology Bulletin*, 10(3), 234-243. <https://doi.org/10.33714/masteb.917788>
- Tahiluddin, A. B., Terzi, E. (2021b). An overview of fisheries and aquaculture in the Philippines. *Journal of Anatolian Environmental and Animal Sciences*, 6(4), 475-486.
- Tahiluddin, A. B., Alawi, T. I., Hassan, N. S. A., Jaji, S. N. A., & Terzi, E. (2021a). Abundance of culturable heterotrophic marine bacteria in *Ulva lactuca* associated with farmed seaweeds *Kappaphycus* spp. and *Eucheuma denticulatum*. *Journal of Agricultural Production*, 2(2), 44-47.
- Tahiluddin, A. B., Diciano, E. J., Robles, R. J. F., & Akrim, J. P. (2021b). Influence of different concentrations of ammonium phosphate on nitrogen assimilation of red seaweed *Kappaphycus striatus*. *Journal of Biometry Studies*, 1(2), 39-44. <https://doi.org/10.29329/JofBS.2021.349.01>

Tahiluddin, A. B., Nuñal, S. N., Luhan, M. R. J., & Santander-de Leon, S. M. S. (2021c). *Vibrio* and heterotrophic marine bacteria composition and abundance in nutrient-enriched *Kappaphycus striatus*. *Philippine Journal of Science*, 150(6B), 1751-1763.

Tahiluddin, A. B., Irin, S. S. H., Jumadil, K. S., Muddihil, R. S., Terzi, E. (2022a). Use of brown seaweed extracts as bio-fertilizers and their effects on the carrageenan yield, ice-ice disease occurrence, and growth rate of the red seaweed *Kappaphycus striatus*. *Yuzuncu Yil University Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 32(2), 436-447.

Tahiluddin, A. B., Nuñal, S. N., & Santander-de Leon, S. M. S. (2022b). Inorganic nutrient enrichment of seaweed *Kappaphycus*: Farmers' practices and effects on growth and ice-ice disease occurrence. *Regional Studies in Marine Science* (In press). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rsma.2022.102593>

Trono, G. C., & Largo, D. B. (2019). The seaweed resources of the Philippines. *Botanica Marina*, 62(5), 483-498. <https://doi.org/10.1515/bot-2018-0069>

Yangson, N. A. T., Edubos, J. I., Tahiluddin, A. B., Toring, C. C., & Toring-Farquerabao, M. L. B. (2022). A preliminary study on the cultivation of brown seaweed *Sargassum cristaefolium* using fixed-off bottom and raft methods. *Journal of Agricultural Production*, 3(1), 17-29.

Zainuddin, E. N., Anshary, H., Huyyirnah, H., Hiola, R., & Baxa, D. V. (2019). Antibacterial activity of *Caulerpa racemosa* against pathogenic bacteria promoting "ice-ice" disease in the red alga *Gracilaria verrucosa*. *Journal of Applied Phycology*, 31(5), 3201-3212.